

Questionnaire

1 Intro

Dear #u_name#,

Thank you very much for agreeing to participate in this survey on film festival research.

Your response is essential to us. We respect your time and value your trust. We will do our best to walk you through this survey in a fast and transparent manner.

During the survey, you will be able to go back and change/complete your answers if needed. The survey will take about 15 minutes to finish.

Non-personal film-related data (e.g., festival run) will be accessed only by the research team and published at the aggregate level. You can choose to share your data with other qualified researchers to ensure transparency and reusability of our findings. Such data sharing is restricted to research purposes only and is managed via a documented process. One of the survey questions will ask you to give or withdraw your consent for such data sharing.

The primary focus of this study are festival screenings. In a few questions, we ask to provide contact data, to make the data collection process easier for you or to inquire about your interest to participate in our follow-up study. These personal data (i.e., your contact details) are collected solely based on your consent, will not be passed to third parties, will be treated confidentially and will be deleted latest after two years.

The Film University Babelsberg KONRAD WOLF processes personal data under the regulations of the EU General Data Protection Regulation and the Data Privacy Law of the German state of Brandenburg (BbgDSG). You may demand at any time, that your personal data are corrected, deleted or blocked. You have the right to change or withdraw your consent at any time by contacting the team or data protection officer by e-mail or mail using the below mentioned contact addresses. No other costs than the regular postage or basic applicable tariffs for the means of communication chosen may be imposed on you by the Film University.

Research team:

Email: filmcirculation@filmuniversitaet.de

Postal address: Circulation (Drittmittel-Projekt), Filmuniversität Babelsberg KONRAD WOLF, Marlene-Dietrich-Allee 11, 14482 Potsdam

Film University's Data Protection Officer:

Email: datenschutz@filmuniversitaet.de

Postal address: Filmuniversität Babelsberg KONRAD WOLF, Datenschutz, Marlene-Dietrich-Allee 11, 14482 Potsdam

Please click "Continue" to start the survey.

Yours,

Prof. Dr. Skadi Loist (s.loist(at)filmuniversitaet.de)
Zhenya Samoiloova, Ph.D. (e.samoiloova(at)filmuniversitaet.de)

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2 Information about films

In the following sets of questions, we would like to learn about the circulation of the film:

"#u_film_title#" (by #u_director_name_#, #u_prod_year_#).

If you have information on film festival participation and awards, having such data at hand when starting the survey will help you go through the survey faster.

During the survey, you can also choose to send information to us via email or being contacted by us via phone. If you have no or only partial information about festivals, your participation in the survey is still very valuable to us.

3 available info

What information about festival screenings of your film do you have?

Example of information we are looking for:

The film was screened at the festival "Y" in February 2013 in Berlin, Germany.

- I have no information
- I have partial or complete information
- I do not know

4 Filter Filter

v_11 availability fest runs **What information about festival screenings of your film do you have?** unequal 1

- availability fest runs (From page 3: available info)

4.1 imdb

Would you like us to enter festival data of your film to the internet movie database (IMDb)?

If the film is not in the IMDb, we would create a page for it.

If it already has festivals entered, we would add the missing festival screenings.

Yes

No

other (please specify)

5 Filter Filter

v_11 availability fest runs **What information about festival screenings of your film do you have?** unequal 1
- availability fest runs (From page 3: available info)

5.1 fest number

At how many festivals was your film screened?

If you don't know the exact number, enter your best estimate.

5.2 fest format

How would you like to share the festival participation data with us?

send a document with festival information by email

fill in an offline or paper-based form

enter data manually within this survey

communicate it via a phone call

5.2.1 Filter Filter

v_13 fest data format How would you like to share the festival participation data with us? - fest data format (From page 5.2: fest format) equal 1
or v_13 fest data format How would you like to share the festival participation data with us? - fest data format (From page 5.2: fest format) equal 2

or v_13 fest data format How would you like to share the festival participation data with us? - fest data format (From page 5.2: fest format) equal 3

or v_13 fest data format How would you like to share the festival participation data with us? - fest data format (From page 5.2: fest format) equal 4

5.2.1.1 contacts and manual entry

For each festival your film "#u_film_title#" was screened at, enter available (even, if incomplete) information on festival name, location, date, and award(s).

You can enter 10 festivals per page. If you have more to report, click "I would like to report more festivals" at the end of the page.

If you want to choose a different way to share the data with us (email, phone, or offline form), click "Back" and select a different format.

	full festival name	festival location (city, country)	date MM/YYYY (e.g. 12/2013)	festival award(s)
Festival 1	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 2	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 3	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 4	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 5	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 6	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 7	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 8	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 9	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 10	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry?

- I would like to report more festivals
- I am finished with all of the festivals

Please send your file to filmcirculation@filmuniversitaet.de.

Do not worry if your file is not complete or the format is unusual.

We are interested in information on festival name, festival location, date MM/YYYY, and awards (if there were any).

Please provide email address and contact name, so that we can send you the form to fill out.

The contact data will be deleted after six months, will be treated confidentially, and will not be disclosed to third parties.

email address

contact name

Please provide phone number and contact name, so that we could contact you.

The contact data will be deleted after six months, will be treated confidentially, and will not be disclosed to third parties.

phone number (including country and
area code)

contact name

5.2.1.1.1 Filter Filter

v_853 more to report Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry? - more to report (From page 5.2.1.1: contacts and manual entry) equal 1

5.2.1.1.1.1 manual entry 2

You can enter 10 festivals per page. If you have more to report, click "I would like to report more festivals" at the end of the page.

	full festival name	festival location (city, country)	date MM/YYYY (e.g. 12/2013)	festival award(s) if any
Festival 11	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 12	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 13	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 14	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 15	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 16	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Festival 17	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 18	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 19	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 20	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry?

- I would like to report more festivals
- I am finished with all of the festivals

5.2.1.1.1.1.1 Filter Filter

v_1032 more to report 2 Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry? - more to report 2 (From page 5.2.1.1.1.1: manual entry 2) equal 1

5.2.1.1.1.1.1 manual entry 3

You can enter 10 festivals per page. If you have more to report, click "I would like to report more" at the end of the page.

	full festival name	festival location (city, country)	date MM/YYYY (e.g. 12/2013)	festival award(s) if any
Festival 21	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 22	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 23	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 24	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 25	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 26	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 27	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 28	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 29	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Festival 30

Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry?

- I would like to report more festivals
- I am finished with all of the festivals

5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1 Filter Filter

v_1113 more to report 3 Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry? - more to report 3 (From page 5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1: manual entry equal 1

5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1 manual entry 4

You can enter 10 festivals per page. If you have more to report, click "I would like to report more" at the end of the page.

	full festival name	festival location (city, country)	date MM/YYYY (e.g. 12/2013)	festival award(s) if any
Festival 31	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 32	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 33	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 34	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 35	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 36	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 37	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 38	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 39	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 40	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry?

- I would like to report more festivals

I am finished with all of the festivals

5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1 Filter Filter

v_1352 more to report 4 Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry? - more to report 4 (From page 5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1: manual entry 4) equal 1

5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1 manual entry of festivals 5

You can enter 10 festivals per page. If you have more to report, click "I would like to report more" at the end of the page.

	full festival name	festival location (city, country)	date MM/YYYY (e.g. 12/2013)	festival award(s) if any
Festival 41	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 42	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 43	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 44	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 45	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 46	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 47	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 48	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 49	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Festival 50	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry?

I would like to report more festivals

I am finished with all of the festivals

5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.2 Filter Filter

v_1393 more to
report 5

Would you like to report more festivals or complete your entry? - more to report 5 (From page 5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1: manual entry of festivals 5) equal 1

5.2.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.1.2.1 manual entry of festivals 6

Please enter the rest of the festivals below.

Just as in the previous pages, for each festival indicate name, festival location, date MM/YYYY, and awards (if there are any).

5.2.1.2 Filter Filter

v_13 fest data format How would you like to share the festival participation data with us? - fest data format (From page 5.2: fest format) equal 1

5.2.1.2.1 contact for email format

Please, provide us with your contact details for us to identify your email and match your file to the correct film.

Your contact data will be deleted six three months, will be treated confidentially, and will not be disclosed to third parties.

contact name

email address

5.2.1.3 Filter Filter

v_13 fest data format How would you like to share the festival participation data with us? - fest data format (From page 5.2: fest format) equal 3

5.2.1.3.1 contact for manual entry format

Contacting you in case of unclear entry or possible error(s) would help us make best use of the shared information. Please provide your preferred contact details for us to approach you.

We will contact you only if missing information prevents us from using your data altogether. Your contact data will be deleted after six months, will be treated confidentially, and will not be disclosed to third parties.

contact name

email address

phone number (incl. country and area
code)

5.2.1.4 Filter Filter

- | | | |
|--------------------------------|---|---------|
| v_11 availability fest runs | What information about festival screenings of your film do you have?
- availability fest runs (From page 3: available info) | equal 2 |
| or v_11 availability fest runs | What information about festival screenings of your film do you have?
- availability fest runs (From page 3: available info) | equal 3 |

5.2.1.4.1 where does the data come from

Does the information that you provided or plan to provide include all film festivals where your film screened?

- Yes
- No
- I do not know

Which sources(s) did you use to find information about the festival run of your film?

- personal/company documentation
- film website
- IMDb film page
- other (please specify):

5.2.1.4.1.1 Filter Filter

- | | | |
|----------------------------------|--|---------|
| v_1394 complete festival runs | Does the information that you provided or plan to provide include all film festivals where your film screened? - complete festival runs (From page 5.2.1.4.1: where does the data come from) | equal 2 |
| or v_1394 complete festival runs | Does the information that you provided or plan to provide include all film festivals where your film screened? - complete festival runs (From page 5.2.1.4.1: where does the data come from) | equal 3 |

5.2.1.4.1.1.1 clarification for partial data

Please describe possible limitations and gaps in your festival list.

Which of the persons or entities listed below (if any), might have the missing information on the festival run of your film?

- world sales
- distribution company(ies)
- film director(s)
- other (please specify):
- none of the above

6 screening and submission fees categorical

Did the film collect any festival screening fees?

Here we mean fees **paid by the festival(s)** to the film representatives

- Yes
- No
- I do not have this information

Was the film charged any festival submission fees?

Here we mean fees charged **by the festival(s)** to submit a film.

- Yes
- No
- I do not have this information

Were festival submissions limited by the budget?

For example, you wanted to submit the film to a festival, but did not do so, because you could not pay the submission fee.

- Yes
- No
- I do not have this information

6.1 Filter Filter

v_481 screening fees Did the film collect any festival screening fees? - screening fees (From page 6: screening and submission fees categorical) equal 2

6.1.1 screening fees amount

**What was the total amount of the festival screening fees collected by the film?
Use any currency you prefer.**

If you do not know the exact number, please give us your best estimate

amount

Select currency for the reported amount

United States dollar
Euro
Canadian dollar
British pound
Indian rupee
Afghan afghani
Albanian lek
Algerian dinar
Angolan kwanza
Argentine peso
Armenian dram
Aruban florin
Australian dollar
Azerbaijani manat
Bahamian dollar
Barbadian dollar
Belarusian ruble
Belize dollar
Bermudian dollar
Bhutanese ngultrum
Bolivian boliviano

Bosnia and Herzegovina convertible mark
Botswana pula
Brazilian real
Brunei dollar
Bulgarian lev
Burmese kyat
Burundian franc
Cambodian riel
Cape Verdean escudo
Cayman Islands dollar
Central African
CFA franc
CFP franc
Chilean peso
Chinese yuan
Colombian peso
Comorian franc
Congolese franc
Cook Islands dollar
Costa Rican colón
Croatian kuna
Cuban convertible peso
Cuban peso
Czech koruna
Danish krone
Djiboutian franc
Dominican peso
Eastern Caribbean dollar
Egyptian pound
Eritrean nakfa
Ethiopian birr
Falkland Islands pound
Faroese króna
Fijian dollar
Gambian dalasi
Georgian lari
Ghanaian cedi
Gibraltar pound
Guatemalan quetzal
Guernsey pound
Guinean franc
Guyanese dollar
Haitian gourde
Honduran lempira
Hong Kong dollar
Hungarian forint

Armenian dram
Icelandic króna
Indonesian rupiah
Iranian rial
Iraqi dinar
Israeli new shekel
Jamaican dollar
Japanese yen
Jersey pound
Jordanian dinar
Kazakhstani tenge
Kenyan shilling
Kuwaiti dinar
Kyrgyzstani som
Lao kip
Lebanese pound
Lesotho loti
Liberian dollar
Libyan dinar
Macanese pataca
Macedonian denar
Malagasy ariary
Malawian kwacha
Malaysian ringgit
Maldivian rufiyaa
Manx pound
Mauritanian ouguiya
Mauritian rupee
Mexican peso
Moldovan leu
Mongolian tögrög
Moroccan dirham
Mozambican metical
Namibian dollar
Nepalese rupee
Netherlands Antillean guilder
New Taiwan dollar
New Zealand dollar
Nicaraguan córdoba
Nigerian naira
North Korean won
Norwegian krone
Omani rial
Pakistani rupee
Panamanian balboa
Papua New Guinean kina

Paraguayan guaraní
Peruvian sol
Philippine peso
Polish złoty
Qatari riyal
Romanian leu
Russian ruble
Rwandan franc
Sahrawi peseta
Saint Helena pound
Samoan tālā
São Tomé and Príncipe dobra
Saudi riyal
Serbian dinar
Seychellois rupee
Sierra Leonean leone
Singapore dollar
Solomon Islands dollar
Somali shilling
Somaliland shilling
South African rand
South Korean won
South Sudanese pound
Sri Lankan rupee
Sudanese pound
Surinamese dollar
Swazi lilangeni
Swedish krona
Swiss franc
Syrian pound
Tajikistani somoni
Tanzanian shilling
Thai baht
Tongan pa'anga
Transnistrian ruble
Trinidad and Tobago dollar
Tunisian dinar
Turkish lira
Turkmenistan manat
Tuvaluan dollar
Ugandan shilling
Ukrainian hryvnia
United Arab Emirates dirham
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm

Vanuatu vatu
Venezuelan bolívar soberano
Vietnamese đồng
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm
Vanuatu vatu
Venezuelan bolívar soberano
Vietnamese đồng
West African CFA franc
Yemeni rial
Zambian kwacha
Zimbabwean bonds

6.2 Filter Filter

v_1124 submission
fees

Was the film charged any festival submission fees? - submission fees (From page 6: screening and submission fees categorical) equal 2

6.2.1 submission fees amount

**What was the total amount of the submission fees for the film?
Use any currency you prefer.**

If you do not know the exact number, please give us your best estimate.

amount

Select currency for the reported amount

United States dollar
Euro
Canadian dollar
British pound
Indian rupee
Afghan afghani
Albanian lek
Algerian dinar
Angolan kwanza
Argentine peso
Armenian dram
Aruban florin
Australian dollar
Azerbaijani manat
Bahamian dollar
Barbadian dollar
Belarusian ruble
Belize dollar

Bermudian dollar
Bhutanese ngultrum
Bolivian boliviano
Bosnia and Herzegovina convertible mark
Botswana pula
Brazilian real
Brunei dollar
Bulgarian lev
Burmese kyat
Burundian franc
Cambodian riel
Cape Verdean escudo
Cayman Islands dollar
Central African
CFA franc
CFP franc
Chilean peso
Chinese yuan
Colombian peso
Comorian franc
Congoese franc
Cook Islands dollar
Costa Rican colón
Croatian kuna
Cuban convertible peso
Cuban peso
Czech koruna
Danish krone
Djiboutian franc
Dominican peso
Eastern Caribbean dollar
Egyptian pound
Eritrean nakfa
Ethiopian birr
Falkland Islands pound
Faroese króna
Fijian dollar
Gambian dalasi
Georgian lari
Ghanaian cedi
Gibraltar pound
Guatemalan quetzal
Guernsey pound
Guinean franc
Guyanese dollar
Haitian gourde

Haitian gourde
Honduran lempira
Hong Kong dollar
Hungarian forint
Icelandic króna
Indonesian rupiah
Iranian rial
Iraqi dinar
Israeli new shekel
Jamaican dollar
Japanese yen
Jersey pound
Jordanian dinar
Kazakhstani tenge
Kenyan shilling
Kuwaiti dinar
Kyrgyzstani som
Lao kip
Lebanese pound
Lesotho loti
Liberian dollar
Libyan dinar
Macanese pataca
Macedonian denar
Malagasy ariary
Malawian kwacha
Malaysian ringgit
Maldivian rufiyaa
Manx pound
Mauritanian ouguiya
Mauritian rupee
Mexican peso
Moldovan leu
Mongolian tögrög
Moroccan dirham
Mozambican metical
Namibian dollar
Nepalese rupee
Netherlands Antillean guilder
New Taiwan dollar
New Zealand dollar
Nicaraguan córdoba
Nigerian naira
North Korean won
Norwegian krone
Omani rial

Ukrainian hryvnia
Pakistani rupee
Panamanian balboa
Papua New Guinean kina
Paraguayan guaraní
Peruvian sol
Philippine peso
Polish złoty
Qatari riyal
Romanian leu
Russian ruble
Rwandan franc
Sahrawi peseta
Saint Helena pound
Samoan tālā
São Tomé and Príncipe dobra
Saudi riyal
Serbian dinar
Seychellois rupee
Sierra Leonean leone
Singapore dollar
Solomon Islands dollar
Somali shilling
Somaliland shilling
South African rand
South Korean won
South Sudanese pound
Sri Lankan rupee
Sudanese pound
Surinamese dollar
Swazi lilangeni
Swedish krona
Swiss franc
Syrian pound
Tajikistani somoni
Tanzanian shilling
Thai baht
Tongan pa'anga
Transnistrian ruble
Trinidad and Tobago dollar
Tunisian dinar
Turkish lira
Turkmenistan manat
Tuvaluan dollar
Ugandan shilling
Ukrainian hryvnia

United Arab Emirates dirham
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm
Vanuatu vatu
Venezuelan bolívar soberano
Vietnamese đồng
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm
Vanuatu vatu
Venezuelan bolívar soberano
Vietnamese đồng
West African CFA franc
Yemeni rial
Zambian kwacha
Zimbabwean bonds

7 film budget ranges

Which of these describes your budget film (excluding marketing costs)?

Amounts are in Euro

- 0 - 49.999 Euro
- 50.000 - 199.999 Euro
- 200.000 - 499.999 Euro
- 500.000 - 999.999 Euro
- 1.000.000 - 2.999.999 Euro
- 3.000.000 - 9.999.999 Euro
- 10.000.000 - 29.999.999 Euro
- 30.000.000 Euro or more

8 film budget amount

If possible, specify your film's budget amount (without marketing costs). Use any currency you prefer.

If you do not know the exact number, please give us your best estimate.

amount

Select currency for the reported amount

United States dollar
Euro
Canadian dollar
British pound
Indian rupee
Afghan afghani
Albanian lek
Algerian dinar
Angolan kwanza
Argentine peso
Armenian dram
Aruban florin
Australian dollar
Azerbaijani manat
Bahamian dollar
Barbadian dollar
Belarusian ruble
Belize dollar
Bermudian dollar
Bhutanese ngultrum
Bolivian boliviano
Bosnia and Herzegovina convertible mark
Botswana pula
Brazilian real
Brunei dollar
Bulgarian lev
Burmese kyat
Burundian franc
Cambodian riel
Cape Verdean escudo
Cayman Islands dollar
Central African
CFA franc
CFP franc
Chilean peso
Chinese yuan
Colombian peso
Comorian franc
Congoese franc
Cook Islands dollar
Costa Rican colón

Costa Rican colón
Croatian kuna
Cuban convertible peso
Cuban peso
Czech koruna
Danish krone
Djiboutian franc
Dominican peso
Eastern Caribbean dollar
Egyptian pound
Eritrean nakfa
Ethiopian birr
Falkland Islands pound
Faroese króna
Fijian dollar
Gambian dalasi
Georgian lari
Ghanaian cedi
Gibraltar pound
Guatemalan quetzal
Guernsey pound
Guinean franc
Guyanese dollar
Haitian gourde
Honduran lempira
Hong Kong dollar
Hungarian forint
Icelandic króna
Indonesian rupiah
Iranian rial
Iraqi dinar
Israeli new shekel
Jamaican dollar
Japanese yen
Jersey pound
Jordanian dinar
Kazakhstani tenge
Kenyan shilling
Kuwaiti dinar
Kyrgyzstani som
Lao kip
Lebanese pound
Lesotho loti
Liberian dollar
Libyan dinar
Macanese pataca

Macedonian denar
Malagasy ariary
Malawian kwacha
Malaysian ringgit
Maldivian rufiyaa
Manx pound
Mauritanian ouguiya
Mauritian rupee
Mexican peso
Moldovan leu
Mongolian tögrög
Moroccan dirham
Mozambican metical
Namibian dollar
Nepalese rupee
Netherlands Antillean guilder
New Taiwan dollar
New Zealand dollar
Nicaraguan córdoba
Nigerian naira
North Korean won
Norwegian krone
Omani rial
Pakistani rupee
Panamanian balboa
Papua New Guinean kina
Paraguayan guaraní
Peruvian sol
Philippine peso
Polish złoty
Qatari riyal
Romanian leu
Russian ruble
Rwandan franc
Sahrawi peseta
Saint Helena pound
Samoan tālā
São Tomé and Príncipe dobra
Saudi riyal
Serbian dinar
Seychellois rupee
Sierra Leonean leone
Singapore dollar
Solomon Islands dollar
Somali shilling
South African rand

Somaliand shilling
South African rand
South Korean won
South Sudanese pound
Sri Lankan rupee
Sudanese pound
Surinamese dollar
Swazi lilangeni
Swedish krona
Swiss franc
Syrian pound
Tajikistani somoni
Tanzanian shilling
Thai baht
Tongan pa'anga
Transnistrian ruble
Trinidad and Tobago dollar
Tunisian dinar
Turkish lira
Turkmenistan manat
Tuvaluan dollar
Ugandan shilling
Ukrainian hryvnia
United Arab Emirates dirham
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm
Vanuatu vatu
Venezuelan bolívar soberano
Vietnamese đồng
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm
Vanuatu vatu
Venezuelan bolívar soberano
Vietnamese đồng
West African CFA franc
Yemeni rial
Zambian kwacha
Zimbabwean bonds

9 marketing costs

Did the film have any marketing costs?

Yes

No

I do not have this information

9.1 Filter Filter

v_1442 marketing costs yes - no Did the film have any marketing costs? - marketing costs yes - no (From page 9: marketing costs) equal 1

9.1.1 marketing costs amount

**What were the marketing costs of the film?
Use any currency you prefer.**

If you do not know the exact number, please give us your best estimate.

amount

Select currency for the reported amount

United States dollar
Euro
Canadian dollar
British pound
Indian rupee
Afghan afghani
Albanian lek
Algerian dinar
Angolan kwanza
Argentine peso
Armenian dram
Aruban florin
Australian dollar
Azerbaijani manat
Bahamian dollar
Barbadian dollar
Belarusian ruble
Belize dollar
Bermudian dollar
Bhutanese ngultrum
Bolivian boliviano
Bosnia and Herzegovina convertible mark
Botswana pula
Brazilian real
Brunei dollar
Bulgarian lev
Burmese kvat

Burmese kyat
Burundian franc
Cambodian riel
Cape Verdean escudo
Cayman Islands dollar
Central African
CFA franc
CFP franc
Chilean peso
Chinese yuan
Colombian peso
Comorian franc
Congoese franc
Cook Islands dollar
Costa Rican colón
Croatian kuna
Cuban convertible peso
Cuban peso
Czech koruna
Danish krone
Djiboutian franc
Dominican peso
Eastern Caribbean dollar
Egyptian pound
Eritrean nakfa
Ethiopian birr
Falkland Islands pound
Faroese króna
Fijian dollar
Gambian dalasi
Georgian lari
Ghanaian cedi
Gibraltar pound
Guatemalan quetzal
Guernsey pound
Guinean franc
Guyanese dollar
Haitian gourde
Honduran lempira
Hong Kong dollar
Hungarian forint
Icelandic króna
Indonesian rupiah
Iranian rial
Iraqi dinar
Israeli new shekel

Jamaican dollar
Japanese yen
Jersey pound
Jordanian dinar
Kazakhstani tenge
Kenyan shilling
Kuwaiti dinar
Kyrgyzstani som
Lao kip
Lebanese pound
Lesotho loti
Liberian dollar
Libyan dinar
Macanese pataca
Macedonian denar
Malagasy ariary
Malawian kwacha
Malaysian ringgit
Maldivian rufiyaa
Manx pound
Mauritanian ouguiya
Mauritian rupee
Mexican peso
Moldovan leu
Mongolian tögrög
Moroccan dirham
Mozambican metical
Namibian dollar
Nepalese rupee
Netherlands Antillean guilder
New Taiwan dollar
New Zealand dollar
Nicaraguan córdoba
Nigerian naira
North Korean won
Norwegian krone
Omani rial
Pakistani rupee
Panamanian balboa
Papua New Guinean kina
Paraguayan guaraní
Peruvian sol
Philippine peso
Polish złoty
Qatari riyal
Romanian leu

Romanian leu
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Rwandan franc
Sahrawi peseta
Saint Helena pound
Samoan tālā
São Tomé and Príncipe dobra
Saudi riyal
Serbian dinar
Seychellois rupee
Sierra Leonean leone
Singapore dollar
Solomon Islands dollar
Somali shilling
Somaliland shilling
South African rand
South Korean won
South Sudanese pound
Sri Lankan rupee
Sudanese pound
Surinamese dollar
Swazi lilangeni
Swedish krona
Swiss franc
Syrian pound
Tajikistani somoni
Tanzanian shilling
Thai baht
Tongan pa'anga
Transnistrian ruble
Trinidad and Tobago dollar
Tunisian dinar
Turkish lira
Turkmenistan manat
Tuvaluan dollar
Ugandan shilling
Ukrainian hryvnia
United Arab Emirates dirham
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm
Vanuatu vatu
Venezuelan bolívar soberano
Vietnamese đồng
Uruguayan peso
Uzbekistani so'm
Vanuatu vatu

Venezuelan bolívar soberano
 Vietnamese đồng
 West African CFA franc
 Yemeni rial
 Zambian kwacha
 Zimbabwean bonds

10 fest strategy

Did the film use any services of external agencies or consultants to help with festival submissions and/or festival strategy?

- Yes
- No
- I do not have this information

11 markets

Was the film shown at any film markets?

- Yes
- No
- I do not have this information

12 Filter Filter

v_1398 market yes - no Was the film shown at any film markets? - market yes - no (From page 11: markets) equal 1

12.1 manual entry of markets 1

For each film market your film was screened at, enter available (even if incomplete) information on market name, location, and date.

You can enter 10 markets per page. If you have more to report, click "I would like to report more markets" at the end of the page.

	full name	location (if available: city, country)	date MM/YYYY (e.g. 12/2013)
Market 1	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>
Market 2	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Market 3

Market 4

Market 5

Market 6

Market 7

Market 8

Market 9

Market 10

Would you like to report more film markets or complete your entry?

- I would like to report more markets
- I am finished with all of the markets

12.2 Filter Filter

v_1439 market more to report

Would you like to report more film markets or complete your entry? - market more to report (From page 12.1: manual entry of markets 1)

equal 1

12.2.1 manual entry of markets 2

**Please enter the rest of the film markets below.
Just as in the previous pages, for each market indicate name, location, and date MM/YYYY.**

13 film distribution

Besides film festival(s) how was the film distributed?

- via broadcasting on television
- via commercial theatrical release
- as a digital version (streaming/download)
- DVD/Blu-ray
- other (please specify):
- none of the above (only via film festivals)

13.1 Filter Filter

v_937 as a digital version
(streaming/download)

Besides film festival(s) how was the film distributed? - as a digital version (streaming/download) (From page 13: film distribution) equal 1

13.1.1 digital distribution**On which digital platform(s) was your film distributed?**

- Vimeo
- YouTube
- Netflix
- Amazon
- iTunes
- Mubi
- Other, please specify:

14 role in film**Which role(s) in relation to the film do you have?**

- film director
- film producer
- other (please describe your role)
-

15 follow-up qual

Up to now there has been little research on film festivals. Would you like to participate in a follow-up interview?

The interview will not take longer than 30 minutes, unless you are willing to spend more time.
Your contact data will be retained for max 2 years, will be treated confidentially, and will not be disclosed to third parties.

- No
- Yes, contact me via this email:
-

16 publish consent

Upon your consent, we would like to make the film-based data (e.g. festival runs of films, film budget, etc.) accessible to other qualified researchers, so that they could examine, reuse and extend our findings.

These data will include only film-specific information you shared and will not include any of your personal data such as names and contacts. Such data sharing is restricted to research purposes only and is managed via a documented process. Even if you agree to share your data now, you can withdraw your consent later until 31. August 2020 by writing to filmcirculation@filmuniversitaet.de or datenschutz@filmuniversitaet.de.

- I agree to make film-specific data accessible to research community
- I do not agree to make film-specific data accessible to research community
-

17 final page

Thank you for taking time to support our study.

This is the last page of the survey.

Click "Submit" to submit your responses.

You can also click "Back" to go back to your answers to review/complete/change them.

18 Final page

Thank you. You have successfully submitted the survey.
